

Synthesis of *N*-galactosylated isodithiobiurets

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Abstract : Several 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets have been prepared by the interaction of aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl isothiocyanate. The structures of the newly synthesized compounds have been established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Keywords : *N*-Galactosides, aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides, galactosyl isothiocyanate, isodithiobiurets.

Introduction

Glycosyl carbamides and glycosyl thiocarbamides have great pharmacological and biochemical aspects¹. Many of these derivatives have been found to possess wide applications in industry as carbohydrate based detergent² and in medicine as anticancer agent³ and antifungal agents⁴.

Galactosyl isothiocyanate⁵, likewise other glycosyl isothiocyanates has a significant role in synthetic carbohydrate chemistry. Many compounds have been synthesized by the use of galactosyl isothiocyanate, for example, galactosyl isocyanide⁶, galactosyl amino derivatives⁷ and other heterocycles⁸. But there is no report on the synthesis of isodithiobiurets having β -galactosyl substituent. On the basis of knowledge gained on the work done on *N*-glucosylated isodithiobiurets^{9,10}, it was quite interesting to synthesize some new *N*-galactosylated thioamides.

In the present communication, we report the synthesis of 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets by the interaction of tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl isothiocyanate and aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides. All the products obtained have been crystallized from alcohol. IR spectra of the products show characteristic absorption of prominent peaks, ¹H NMR spectra show characteristic peaks due to N-H, acetyl and glycosidic protons, while the ESI Mass spectra show peaks due to acetogalactose unit at *m/z* 331, 211, 169, 109¹¹⁻¹³.

Results and discussion

Several 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1) were prepared by the condensation of aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides (**1a-g**) and tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactosyl isothiocyanate (**2**) in benzene for 4 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC, after complete reaction, the solvent was distilled off and the resultant sticky residue was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) to afford the products (**3a-g**). All the products were crystallized from alcohol. Structures of all products synthesized were established on the basis of usual chemical transformations and IR, NMR and Mass spectral studies.

Experimental

General methods :

Melting points are uncorrected. Optical rotations $[\alpha]_D$ were measured on a Equip-Tronics digital polarimeter model No. EQ 800 in CHCl₃ at 39 °C. IR spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer spectrum RXI (4000–450 cm⁻¹) FTIR spectrometer. ¹H NMR were obtained on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR) NMR spectrometer for a sample in CDCl₃ solution with TMS as an internal reference. The mass spectra were recorded on a Micromass Quattro II triple quadrupole mass spectrometer.

Aryl-*S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides (**1a-g**) :

The required aryl *S*-benzyl isothiocarbamides (**1a-g**)

Note

Scheme 1

where, R = (a) phenyl, (b) *o*-Cl-phenyl, (c) *m*-Cl-phenyl, (d) *p*-Cl-phenyl, (e) *o*-tolyl, (f) *m*-tolyl, (g) *p*-tolyl.

Ac = -COCH₃; Bz = -CH₂C₆H₅

were prepared by the already known method¹⁴, which involves interaction of benzyl chloride with aryl thiocarbamides in ethanol, refluxed for 90 min, followed by the basification of the resultant solution using dilute ammonium hydroxide to give the isothiocarbamides (1a-g).

Tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (2):

Tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-galactosyl isothiocyanate (2) was prepared by employing the classical Fischer's method¹⁵ using lead thiocyanate instead of silver thiocyanate in anhydrous Xylene medium.

1-Aryl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (3a-g) (Scheme 1):

Condensation of aryl-S-benzyl isothiocarbamides (1a-g, 0.005 M) and tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanate (2, 0.005 M, 2 g), in benzene (20 mL) was carried out on boiling water bath for 4 h. The reaction was monitored by TLC, after complete reaction, the solvent was distilled off and the resultant sticky residue was triturated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80 °C) to afford the products (3a-g). All the products were crystallized from alcohol before recording the physical data (Table 1). The purity of compounds (3a-g) was checked by TLC.

The compounds formed have β configuration, which is confirmed from the high value of vicinal coupling constant of proton at anomeric position^{16,17}.

1-Phenyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (3a):

IR (KBr): ν 3336 (N-H), 2929 (Ar-H), 1749 (C=O), 1551 (C=N), 1366 (C-N), 1223 (C-O), 1044 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 7.43–7.23 (11H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.97 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.72 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.49 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.43–5.14 (2H, m, H₂, H₃), 4.35–3.95 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.17–1.60 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃). ESI Mass (*m/z*): 632 (M⁺ + 1), 331, 211, 169, 109, 91 (Found: C, 54.99; H, 5.16; N, 6.51; S, 10.01. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₃N₃O₉S₂: C, 55.15; H, 5.22; N, 6.65; S, 10.14%).

1-o-Cl-Phenyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl-β-D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (3b):

¹H NMR (CDCl₃): δ 7.43–7.22 (10H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.38 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.71 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.50 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.43–5.10 (2H, m, H₂, H₃), 4.35–4.01 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.16–1.97 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃) (Found: C, 52.33; H, 4.78; N, 6.13; S, 9.52. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂N₃O₉S₂Cl: C, 52.33; H, 4.78; N, 6.13; S, 9.52).

Table 1. Physical data of 1-aryl-5-tetra-*O*-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-2-*S*-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiurets (**3a-g**) (Scheme 1)

Reactants : (i) Aryl- <i>S</i> -benzyl isothiocarbamides (1a-g , 0.005 <i>M</i>), (ii) tetra- <i>O</i> -acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl isothiocyanates (2 , 0.005 <i>M</i> , 2 g)						
Sr. no.	Reactant 1a-g (g)	Product 3a-g	M.p. ($^{\circ}$ C)	Yield g (%)	$[\alpha]_D^{39}$ (c, CHCl ₃)	<i>R</i> _f (3 : 2, CCl ₄ : EtOAc)
1.	1a (1.21)	3a	174–176	2.1 (65.6)	122.2 $^{\circ}$ (0.9)	0.83
2.	1b (1.38)	3b	116–118	2.5 (73.5)	-21.5 $^{\circ}$ (0.93)	0.84
3.	1c (1.38)	3c	162–164	2.6 (76.4)	-84.2 $^{\circ}$ (0.95)	0.48
4.	1d (1.38)	3d	158–160	2.2 (64.7)	85.1 $^{\circ}$ (0.94)	0.53
5.	1e (1.28)	3e	136–138	2.1 (63.6)	52.0 $^{\circ}$ (0.96)	0.71
6.	1f (1.28)	3f	150–152	2.4 (72.7)	-33.3 $^{\circ}$ (0.9)	0.77
7.	1g (1.28)	3g	138–140	2.5 (75.7)	43.0 $^{\circ}$ (0.93)	0.70

52.28; H, 4.84; N, 6.31; S, 9.62%).

1-m-Cl-Phenyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4 isodithiobiuret (3c) :

IR (KBr) : ν 3336 (N-H), 2930 (Ar-H), 1751 (C=O), 1548 (C=N), 1366 (C-N), 1223 (C-O), 1045 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.38–7.16 (10H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.38 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.69 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.49 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.43–5.10 (2H, m, H₂, H₃), 4.32–4.00 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.16–1.67 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃). ESI Mass (*m/z*) : 666 (M⁺), 331, 211, 169, 109, 91 (100%) (Found : C, 52.22; H, 4.88; N, 6.22; S, 9.69. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂N₃O₉S₂Cl : C, 52.28; H, 4.84; N, 6.31; S, 9.62%).

1-p-Cl-phenyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (3d) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.43–7.19 (10H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.38 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.70 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.50 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.44–5.17 (2H, m, H₂, H₃), 4.35–3.99 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.16–1.68 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃) (Found : C, 52.32; H, 4.79; N, 6.40; S, 9.55. Calcd. for C₂₉H₃₂N₃O₉S₂Cl : C, 52.28; H, 4.84; N, 6.31; S, 9.62%).

1-o-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (3e) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.34–7.19 (10H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.97 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.72 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.49 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.40–5.11 (2H,

m, H₂, H₃), 4.30–4.01 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.36 (3H, m, Ar-CH₃), 2.17–1.60 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃) (Found : C, 55.84; H, 5.36; N, 6.42; S, 9.86. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₅N₃O₉S₂ : C, 55.80; H, 5.42; N, 6.51; S, 9.92%).

1-m-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (3f) :

IR (KBr) : ν 3333 (N-H), 2929 (Ar-H), 1749 (C=O), 1550 (C=N), 1365 (C-N), 1221 (C-O), 1046 (C=S); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.36–7.12 (10H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.96 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.72 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.48 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.35–5.13 (2H, m, H₂, H₃), 4.30–4.00 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.36 (3H, m, Ar-CH₃), 2.16–1.62 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃). ESI Mass (*m/z*) : 646 (M⁺+1) (100%), 331, 211, 169, 109, 91 (Found : C, 55.84; H, 5.39; N, 6.59; S, 10.01. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₅N₃O₉S₂ : C, 55.80; H, 5.42; N, 6.51; S, 9.92%).

1-p-Tolyl-5-tetra-O-acetyl- β -D-galactopyranosyl-2-S-benzyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (3g) :

¹H NMR (CDCl₃) : δ 7.34–7.15 (10H, m, N-H(Ar.) and Ar-H), 6.98 (1H, d, *J* 9 Hz, NH(gal.)), 5.72 (1H, t, *J* 9 Hz, H₁), 5.50 (1H, d, *J* 3 Hz, H₄), 5.35–5.10 (2H, m, H₂, H₃), 4.29–4.00 (5H, m, H_{5,6,6'} and Ar-CH₂), 2.34 (3H, m, Ar-CH₃), 2.16–1.61 (12H, m, 4-COCH₃) (Found : C, 55.78; H, 5.48; N, 6.59; S, 9.99. Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₅N₃O₉S₂ : C, 55.80; H, 5.42; N, 6.51; S, 9.92%).

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